

FRACTURE MECHANICS ANALYSIS OF THE CONTACT CRACK IN LAMINATED COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: This paper presents a method to calculate the fracture parameters at interfacial cracks in laminated composites. Depending on the applied loading and crack length, a contact region may develop that changes the nature of the resulting stress intensity factors and energy release rates with respect to the open crack. A combined analytical and numerical model based on frictionless contact was used to eliminate the overlapping of the crack faces where applicable to obtain the correct results. The laminates studied include cross-ply and angle-ply laminates in three point bending containing a central delamination. The present results were compared with results in the literature obtained by the virtual crack closure integral technique for the special case of cross-ply laminates and close agreement was found. In addition, results are given for the extent of the contact zone as well as Mode I and II stress intensity factors and energy release rates as a function of the lamination angle. Overall, the method used provides an effective way to analyze interfacial cracks and delaminations in composite plates subjected to transverse loads or low velocity impacts.

KEYWORDS: fracture mechanics, finite element method, interfacial cracks, delaminations, low velocity impact.

INTRODUCTION

Delamination is a common type of composite damage which can be caused, among other factors, by transverse impacts and manufacturing defects. Due to the resulting degradation in strength and stiffness, analysis and prediction of this type of damage is of significant practical importance in the design of composite structures. An additional area of interest is the analysis of testing specimens used in the determination of fracture toughness [1-3]. However, the analysis of delamination cracks presents many challenges due to the heterogeneous and anisotropic nature of composite materials. A popular way to analyze composite structures of complex geometry and loading is the finite element method; however, the singular behavior that occurs near the crack tip is poorly approximated by conventional finite elements and convergence theorems cease to be applicable in this region [4]. A further complication is that, depending on the loading and material properties, an interlaminar crack may exhibit a region of contact at its faces. Alternative methods based on energy release rate [5-6] require substantial mesh refinement near the crack tip and may lead to non-convergence of the individual mode I and II components for interfacial cracks [3, 7]. In this paper, a method that captures the benefits of finite element analysis away from the crack tip is used in combination with a local analytical solution near the crack tip in order to determine the mixed-mode stress intensity factors and energy release rates of an interfacial crack with a contact region. The method used allows consideration of complex problems with orthotropic materials, arbitrary loading and geometry, and contact at the crack faces.

ANALYTICAL/NUMERICAL PROCEDURE

The method of analysis used is based on finding the global displacement field away from the crack tip by an approximate procedure such as finite elements. In the neighborhood of the crack tip, an elasticity solution is constructed by using an eigenfunction expansion of the stresses and displacements. This expansion is known to within arbitrary constants which are found by matching displacements at the interface, and leads to a set of linear equations in the unknown constants. The contact problem is

formulated so as to satisfy the proper displacement and stress boundary conditions at the crack tip, while the extent of the contact zone is found from a nonlinear finite element model using contact elements at the crack faces. The method is illustrated schematically in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Schematic Illustration of the Method of Analysis Used.

Assuming plane strain conditions, the strain-displacement and equilibrium equations are given by

$$\varepsilon_x = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x}; \quad \varepsilon_y = \frac{\partial v}{\partial y}; \quad \varepsilon_z = 0; \quad \gamma_{yz} = \frac{\partial w}{\partial y}; \quad \gamma_{xz} = \frac{\partial w}{\partial x}; \quad \gamma_{xy} = \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{xy}}{\partial y} = 0; \quad \frac{\partial \tau_{xy}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \sigma_y}{\partial y} = 0; \quad \frac{\partial \tau_{xz}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{yz}}{\partial y} = 0 \quad (2)$$

Furthermore, for an orthotropic linear elastic body Hooke's law becomes:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \sigma_z \\ \tau_{yz} \\ \tau_{xz} \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} c_{11} & c_{12} & c_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ c_{12} & c_{22} & c_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ c_{13} & c_{23} & c_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & c_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & c_{55} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & c_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \varepsilon_z \\ \gamma_{yz} \\ \gamma_{xz} \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1/E_1 & -\nu_{21}/E_2 & -\nu_{31}/E_3 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\nu_{12}/E_1 & 1/E_2 & -\nu_{32}/E_3 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\nu_{13}/E_1 & -\nu_{23}/E_2 & 1/E_3 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{23} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{13} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{12} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \varepsilon_z \\ \gamma_{yz} \\ \gamma_{xz} \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Replacing (1) into (3) and (2) provides the equilibrium equations in terms of displacements

$$c_{11} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + c_{12} \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x \partial y} + c_{66} \left(\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x \partial y} \right) = 0, \quad c_{66} \left(\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x \partial y} + \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} \right) + c_{12} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x \partial y} + c_{22} \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial y^2} = 0, \quad c_{55} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + c_{44} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} = 0 \quad (4)$$

where we note that the equations for u and v are decoupled from that for w . The first two of equations (4) correspond to the in-plane problem, and the third to the out-of-plane problem. In the present work,

only the in-plane problem was considered. Based on the results from Penado [8] and Ting and Chou [9], we can assume that the solution to the in-plane problem in the vicinity of the crack tip is given by

$$u = \zeta_x \left(\frac{Z_p^{1+\lambda_p}}{1+\lambda_p} \right), \quad v = \zeta_y \left(\frac{Z_p^{1+\lambda_p}}{1+\lambda_p} \right) \quad (5)$$

where $Z_p = x + \mu_p y$, μ_p represents the eigenvalues of the elasticity constants to be determined from the equilibrium equations (4), ζ_x and ζ_y are functions of μ_p , and λ_p are eigenvalues to be determined from the boundary conditions near the crack tip. Substituting (5) into the first two of eq. (4) leads to the following homogeneous system of equations

$$\begin{bmatrix} c_{11} + c_{66}\mu_p^2 & (c_{12} + c_{66})\mu_p \\ (c_{12} + c_{66})\mu_p & c_{66} + c_{22}\mu_p^2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \zeta_x \\ \zeta_y \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

For a non-trivial solution of these equations, the determinant of coefficients must be zero. This leads to the following quartic equation in μ_p :

$$c_{22}c_{66}\mu_p^4 + (c_{11}c_{22} - 2c_{12}c_{66} - c_{12}^2)\mu_p^2 + c_{11}c_{66} = 0 \quad (7)$$

It can be shown [9] that the μ 's can only be complex or purely imaginary. Therefore, we have two complex conjugate pairs for μ_p . Once the μ_p 's are known, ζ_x and ζ_y can be found from (6) up to arbitrary multiplicative constants. Now, substituting (5) into (1) and (3) gives:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} c_{11}\zeta_x + \mu_p c_{12}\zeta_y \\ c_{12}\zeta_x + \mu_p c_{22}\zeta_y \\ \mu_p c_{66}\zeta_x + c_{66}\zeta_y \end{Bmatrix} Z_p^{\lambda_p} \equiv \begin{Bmatrix} \xi_x \\ \xi_y \\ \xi_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} Z_p^{\lambda_p} \quad (8)$$

It should be noted that in the special case of an isotropic material in the x-y plane having $E_1=E_2=E$, $\nu_{12}=\nu_{21}=\nu$ and $G_{12}=G=E/[2(1+\nu)]$ (for example, the 90° ply in Figure 1), the conjugate pair $\mu_p = \pm i = \pm\sqrt{-1}$ is a double root of (7), and the new solution cannot be obtained by simply inserting isotropic material properties into the equations. In this case, the in-plane displacements given by equations (5) become [9]:

$$u = \zeta_x \left(\frac{Z_p^{1+\lambda_p}}{1+\lambda_p} \right) + \frac{1}{1+\lambda_p} \frac{d}{d\mu_p} \left(\zeta_x Z_p^{1+\lambda_p} \right); \quad v = \zeta_y \left(\frac{Z_p^{1+\lambda_p}}{1+\lambda_p} \right) + \frac{1}{1+\lambda_p} \frac{d}{d\mu_p} \left(\zeta_y Z_p^{1+\lambda_p} \right) \quad (9)$$

The complete asymptotic solutions for displacements and stresses near the crack tip can be obtained by taking linear combinations of the individual solutions to the first two of equations (4) corresponding to the different eigenvalues μ_p (summations over k), and λ_p (summations over m), where k and m are defined below. This leads to the following expressions for the displacements and stresses (note that the results have been converted to cylindrical coordinates with $x = r \cos \theta$ and $y = r \sin \theta$):

$$u_r^{(i)} = \sum_{m=1}^M a_m \left[\frac{r^{1+(\lambda_p)_m}}{1+(\lambda_p)_m} \sum_{k=1}^4 A_{km}^{(i)} (F_r^{(i)})_{km} \right]; \quad u_\theta^{(i)} = \sum_{m=1}^M a_m \left[\frac{r^{1+(\lambda_p)_m}}{1+(\lambda_p)_m} \sum_{k=1}^4 A_{km}^{(i)} (F_\theta^{(i)})_{km} \right] \quad (10)-(11)$$

$$\sigma_r^{(i)} = \sum_{m=1}^M a_m \left[r^{(\lambda_p)_m} \sum_{k=1}^4 A_{km}^{(i)} (G_r^{(i)})_{km} \right]; \quad \sigma_\theta^{(i)} = \sum_{m=1}^M a_m \left[r^{(\lambda_p)_m} \sum_{k=1}^4 A_{km}^{(i)} (G_\theta^{(i)})_{km} \right] \quad (12)-(13)$$

$$\tau_{r\theta}^{(i)} = \sum_{m=1}^M a_m \left[r^{(\lambda_p)_m} \sum_{k=1}^4 A_{km}^{(i)} (G_{r\theta}^{(i)})_{km} \right] \quad (14)$$

where the superscript $i=1,2$ denotes each material region; k and m are dummy indices of summation associated with the eigenvalues of the problem; M is the number of terms in the truncated infinite series; a_m 's are multiplicative constants associated with the in-plane eigenvectors; F_{ij} and G_{ij} are defined in Table 1; and $(\lambda_p)_m$ and A_{km} will be defined later in relation to the boundary conditions at the crack tip.

Table 1. Definitions Used in Equations (10)-(14).

Variable	Orthotropic Materials ¹	Isotropic Materials ²
$(F_r)_k$	$[(\xi_x)_k \cos \theta + (\xi_y)_k \sin \theta](\psi_p)_k^{1+\lambda_p}$	$\frac{1}{2G}[\cos(2 + \lambda_p)\theta \pm i \cdot \sin(2 + \lambda_p)\theta]; \quad k = 1,3$ $\frac{1}{2G}[2(1 - 2\nu) - \lambda_p](\cos \lambda_p \theta \pm i \cdot \sin \lambda_p \theta); \quad k = 2,4$
$(F_\theta)_k$	$[-(\xi_x)_k \sin \theta + (\xi_y)_k \cos \theta](\psi_p)_k^{1+\lambda_p}$	$\frac{1}{2G}[-\sin(2 + \lambda_p)\theta \pm i \cdot \cos(2 + \lambda_p)\theta]; \quad k = 1,3$ $\frac{1}{2G}[4(1 - \nu) + \lambda_p](\sin \lambda_p \theta \mp i \cdot \cos \lambda_p \theta); \quad k = 2,4$
$(G_r)_k$	$[(\xi_x)_k \cos^2 \theta + (\xi_y)_k \sin^2 \theta + 2(\xi_{xy})_k \cos \theta \sin \theta](\psi_p)_k^{\lambda_p}$	$\cos(2 + \lambda_p)\theta \pm i \cdot \sin(2 + \lambda_p)\theta; \quad k = 1,3$ $(2 - \lambda_p)(\cos \lambda_p \theta \pm i \cdot \sin \lambda_p \theta); \quad k = 2,4$
$(G_\theta)_k$	$[(\xi_x)_k \sin^2 \theta + (\xi_y)_k \cos^2 \theta - 2(\xi_{xy})_k \cos \theta \sin \theta](\psi_p)_k^{\lambda_p}$	$-\cos(2 + \lambda_p)\theta \mp i \cdot \sin(2 + \lambda_p)\theta; \quad k = 1,3$ $(2 + \lambda_p)(\cos \lambda_p \theta \pm i \cdot \sin \lambda_p \theta); \quad k = 2,4$
$(G_{r\theta})_k$	$\{[-(\xi_x)_k + (\xi_y)_k] \cos \theta \sin \theta + (\xi_{xy})_k \cos(2\theta)\}(\psi_p)_k^{\lambda_p}$	$-\sin(2 + \lambda_p)\theta \pm i \cdot \cos(2 + \lambda_p)\theta]; \quad k = 1,3$ $\lambda_p (\sin \lambda_p \theta \mp i \cdot \cos \lambda_p \theta); \quad k = 2,4$
¹ $\psi_p = \cos \theta + \mu_p \sin \theta; \quad (\mu_p)_1 = (\bar{\mu}_p)_3, (\mu_p)_2 = (\bar{\mu}_p)_4; \quad \text{Im}[(\mu_p)_1, (\mu_p)_2] > 0; \quad ^2 G = \text{shear modulus} = E / 2(1 + \nu)$		

Two types of boundary conditions must be considered to find all of the unknown parameters: local and remote. The local boundary conditions provide $(\lambda_p)_m$ and A_{km} , and depend on whether the crack faces are stress-free or a contact region near the crack tip exits. In the present problem, either condition may exist depending on the crack length and material properties; this is discussed in more detail in the ‘‘Results and Discussion’’ section. The appropriate local boundary conditions for either case are shown in Table 2 and Figure 2. In Case II, frictionless contact at the crack faces has been assumed [10].

Table 2. Local Boundary Conditions at the Interfacial Corner.

At the crack faces:	
Case I: Crack with stress-free faces	Case II: Crack with contact region
$\sigma_\theta^{(1)}(r, 180^\circ) = \tau_{r\theta}^{(1)}(r, 180^\circ) = 0$ $\sigma_\theta^{(2)}(r, -180^\circ) = \tau_{r\theta}^{(2)}(r, -180^\circ) = 0$	$u_\theta^{(1)}(r, 180^\circ) = u_\theta^{(2)}(r, -180^\circ)$ $\sigma_\theta^{(1)}(r, 180^\circ) = \sigma_\theta^{(2)}(r, -180^\circ)$ $\tau_{r\theta}^{(1)}(r, 180^\circ) = \tau_{r\theta}^{(2)}(r, -180^\circ) = 0$
At the bimaterial interface, either case:	
$\sigma_\theta^{(1)}(r, 0) = \sigma_\theta^{(2)}(r, 0); \quad \tau_{r\theta}^{(1)}(r, 0) = \tau_{r\theta}^{(2)}(r, 0)$ $u_r^{(1)}(r, 0) = u_r^{(2)}(r, 0); \quad u_\theta^{(1)}(r, 0) = u_\theta^{(2)}(r, 0)$	

Figure 2. Local Boundary Conditions near the Crack Tip.

Substitution of equations (10)-(14) into the appropriate equations from Table 2 leads to a homogeneous system of linear equations:

$$r^{\lambda_p} [K_p(\lambda_p)] \{A\} = \{0\} \quad (15)$$

where $[K_p(\lambda_p)]$ is an 8x8 matrix with entries that depend on λ_p , and $\{A\}$ is an 8x1 matrix defined as follows:

$$\{A\} = [A_1^{(1)} \quad A_2^{(1)} \quad A_3^{(1)} \quad A_4^{(1)} \quad A_1^{(2)} \quad A_2^{(2)} \quad A_3^{(2)} \quad A_4^{(2)}]^T \quad (16)$$

For non-trivial solutions to (15), its determinant of coefficients must be zero:

$$|K_p(\lambda_p)| = 0 \quad (17)$$

The solution of equation (17) leads to an infinite number of roots λ_p . These roots were found by truncating the system and using a nonlinear equation solver [11]. Typical eigenvalues are given in Table 3. Then, with the roots known, the eigenvector $\{A\}$ in (15) was found by using singular value decomposition [12-13]. This process, however, only defines the eigenvectors up to arbitrary multiplicative constants (a_m in equations 10-14). These constants were determined from the remote boundary conditions of the model at the global/local interface, as discussed next.

Table 3. First 5 Eigenvalue Pairs for Typical Laminates Used in the Analysis.

Eigenvalue Pair ^a	Any Θ^b , closed crack		$\Theta=0^\circ$, open crack		$\Theta=45^\circ$, open crack	
	Re(λ_p)	Im(λ_p)	Re(λ_p)	Im(λ_p)	Re(λ_p)	Im(λ_p)
1	-0.5	0	-0.5	$\pm 6.56823e-3$	-0.5	$\pm 2.276078e-2$
2	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	0.5	0	0.5	$\pm 6.56823e-3$	0.5	$\pm 2.276078e-2$
4	1	0	1	0	1	0
5	1.5	0	1.5	$\pm 6.56823e-3$	1.5	$\pm 2.276078e-2$

^aNote that a complex conjugate pair is counted as one term and this number of eigenvalues does not correspond to M defined in equations (10) to (14).

^bThe layup is $[\pm\Theta/90]_s$ (see Figure 1).

The determination of the multiplicative constants a_m requires the application of the remote boundary conditions at the global/local interface. This is done by matching displacements of the local and global solutions at the interface (see Figure 1). In the global solution, a nonlinear finite element model with contact elements was used to avoid interpenetration of the crack faces and determine the extent of the

contact region, as discussed in the next section. This way, the appropriate case from Table 2 for the local region was selected. Furthermore, the best results from this match are achieved by using more boundary stations than unknown constants [14-16]. The resulting overdetermined system of equations was satisfied in the present work in a least squares sense by using singular value decomposition [12-13]. A total of $M=30$ terms were used in the eigenfunction expansion, which resulted in an error of less than 2% in satisfying the remote boundary conditions.

FINITE ELEMENT MODEL FOR THE GLOBAL REGION

Figure 3. Mesh, dimensions, loading and boundary conditions used in the global finite element analysis.

The displacement field in the specimen at the boundary of the local region was found by using the finite element model shown in Figure 3. Due to symmetry, only half of the geometry of the beam shown in Figure 1 was considered. The analysis was conducted using the COSMOS/M finite element code [17] and consisted of 852 8-noded quadrilateral plane strain elements and 2,765 nodes. In addition, nonlinear gap elements were used at the crack faces to simulate the contact problem and avoid interpenetration. The element size in the crack region in the x and y directions was, respectively, 0.2 and 0.18 mm. The laminate consisted of six layers having two rows of elements per layer, nominal layer thickness of 0.3645 mm, and layup $[\pm\Theta/90]_s$. The length of the half model was $L=25.4$ mm, and the applied load was $P/2=1$ N. The material properties used, in principal coordinates, were [18]:

$$E_1=119.9 \text{ GPa}, E_2=E_3=9.86 \text{ GPa}, G_{12}=G_{13}=5.24 \text{ GPa}, G_{23}=3.52 \text{ GPa}, \nu_{12}=\nu_{13}=0.3, \nu_{23}=0.4$$

where the subscript 1 refers to the fiber direction. For layup angles, Θ , other than 0° and 90° , coupling of in-plane and out-of-plane effects occurs [19]. The out-of-plane coupling effects caused by off-axis plies were neglected, and effective ply moduli were used as an approximation [19]. The resulting effective properties used are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Effective Material Properties Used in the Analysis.

Property	Layup Angle, Θ						
	0°	15°	30°	45°	60°	75°	90°
E_x (GPa)	119.9	51.7	21.8	13.5	10.8	10.0	9.86
E_y (GPa)	9.86	9.86	9.86	9.86	9.86	9.86	9.86
G_{xy} (GPa)	5.24	5.07	4.67	4.21	3.83	3.60	3.52
ν_{xy}	0.3	0.261	0.262	0.291	0.336	0.380	0.4

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Extent of the Contact Zone

The extent of the contact region was found directly from the finite element results. The differential displacement between the top and bottom faces of the crack for $\Theta=0^\circ$ and 45° is illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Relative displacement of the crack faces, $u_{y \text{ top}} - u_{y \text{ bottom}}$, as a function of crack length for layup angles of (a) 0° and (b) 45° .

For all crack lengths and layup angles, there is a small region under the load that is closed. Outside of this area, the crack can be open or closed, depending on its length and the layup angle. For example, in Figure 4a for $\Theta=0^\circ$, the crack is open outside the region under the load; however, the open region decreases with crack length and completely disappears for $a/L \leq 0.05$, where a is the crack half length. For $\Theta=45^\circ$ (Figure 4b) there is a region near the crack tip that is always closed in addition to the region under the load, yet the crack never became completely closed between these two regions for the range of crack lengths studied ($a/L=0.012$ to 0.4). The results in Figure 4 indicate that two different conditions near the crack tip for the local region must be considered:

- 1) The crack within the local region is closed and contact conditions exist at the crack faces (Figure 4b). The proper boundary conditions for this problem are those indicated in Case II of Figure 2 and Table 2. The resulting singular (negative) eigenvalue, λ_p , from equation (17) is real and no oscillatory behavior results. As shown by Comninou [20], for this crack both the mode I stress intensity factor (SIF) to the right of the tip and the mode II SIF to the left of the tip vanish:

$$K_I^+ = K_{II}^- = 0, \quad \text{but} \quad K_I^- \neq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad K_{II}^+ \neq 0 \quad (18)$$

- 2) The crack tip is open (Figure 4a) and Case I in Figure 2 and Table 2 apply. In this case, the singular eigenvalue, λ_p , from equation (17) is complex, leading to oscillatory stresses and displacements near the crack tip and results in overlapping of crack faces and materials, which is physically inadmissible. Although the crack tip may appear to be completely open in the finite element model, in reality a very small contact region, with maximum extent of the order of 10^{-8} of the crack length, appears [21]. The problem for the small contact zone was treated in an approximate manner, as shown next.

Approximate Analysis of the Interfacial Crack with a Small Contact Region

In cases where the crack appears open at the tip (e.g., Figure 4a) but the singular eigenvalue is complex, a very small contact region appears, the extent of which cannot be determined directly from the finite element results. In these cases, the results for the stress intensity factor can be approximated by considering the J-integral [22] in combination with the results assuming stress free crack faces (Case I in Figure 2 and Table 2). As illustrated in Figure 5, since the J-integral is path-independent for frictionless contact, we have

$$J_{\text{open}} = J_{\text{contact}}$$

Figure 5. Application of the J-integral in the Analysis of the Interfacial Crack with a Small Contact Zone

and since for linear elastic behavior $J=G$ =strain energy release rate, $G_{open} = G_{contact}$. Also, the mode I stress intensity factor just to the right of the crack tip vanishes, $(K_I^+)_{contact} = 0$. Therefore, for orthotropic materials

$$G_{open} = (G_I)_{open} + (G_{II})_{open} = \frac{1}{4}(K_I)_{open}^2 (D_{22} - \beta_{pp}s_1 + \beta_{pp}s_2) + \frac{1}{4}(K_{II})_{open}^2 (D_{11} - \beta_p s_1 + \beta_p s_2) \quad (19)$$

where D_{11} , D_{22} , β_p , β_{pp} , s_1 and s_2 depend on the bimaterial properties and are defined in [23]. Thus,

$$G_{open} = G_{contact} \Rightarrow (K_{II}^+)_{contact} = \sqrt{\frac{(D_{22} - \beta_{pp}s_1 + \beta_{pp}s_2)(K_I)_{open}^2 + (D_{11} - \beta_p s_1 + \beta_p s_2)(K_{II})_{open}^2}{(D_{11} - \beta_p s_1 + \beta_p s_2)}} \quad (20)$$

The above relation is true if the contact zone is within the region dominated by the singular eigenvalue.

Stress Intensity Factor and Energy Release Rate

Once the appropriate constants λ_p , $\{A\}$ and a_m defined earlier, as well as F_{ij} and G_{ij} defined in Table 1, are found, the mode I and II stress intensity factors can be calculated from their definitions in terms of these constants:

$$K_I = (\sqrt{2\pi})a_1 \sum_{k=1}^4 A_{k1} (G_{\theta} |_{\theta=0})_{k1}; \quad K_{II} = (\sqrt{2\pi})a_1 \sum_{k=1}^4 A_{k1} (G_{r\theta} |_{\theta=0})_{k1} \quad (21)$$

For complex $(\lambda_p)_1$, K_I and K_{II} are found by adding the terms associated with the complex conjugate pair of eigenvalues $(\lambda_p)_1$ and $(\lambda_p)_2$, which produces a real value. Results for the stress intensity factors for different layup angles and crack lengths are shown in Figure 6. As indicated earlier, the (+) or (-) superscripts refer, respectively, to locations immediately to the right or left of the crack. In Figure 6a, the discontinuity in K_I around $\Theta=10^\circ$ and $a/L=0.16$ is due to the change in the nature of the crack as it goes from an open crack for $\Theta<10^\circ$ to a closed crack for $\Theta>10^\circ$. A similar situation happens in Figure 6b, where the slight discontinuity in K_I for $\Theta=0^\circ$ and $a/L \approx 0.06$ is due to a similar change except that the crack is closed for $a/L < 0.06$. It is interesting to note in Figure 6b that K_{II}^+ increases with crack length in most cases, indicating unstable crack growth; however, for $\Theta=45^\circ$ and small cracks ($a/L < 0.02$), stable crack growth is observed. Once the stress intensity factors are known, the mode I, mode II and total strain energy release rate can be found by means of equation (19). The results for a layup angle $\Theta=0^\circ$ as a function of crack length are given in Figure 7. As a rough validation of the method of solution, the present results were compared with results from [18], obtained by the virtual crack closure integral

method. Overall, excellent agreement is observed; the small differences can be attributed to the approximate nature of the method used in [18] and the fact that the present results can be expected to be more accurate.

Figure 6. Mode I and II Stress Intensity Factors as a Function of (a) Layup Angle for Two Crack Lengths, (b) Crack Length for Two Layup Angles.

Figure 7. Strain Energy Release Rate for a Layup Angle $\Theta=0^\circ$ (cross-ply laminates) and (a) Short Cracks and (b) Long Cracks.

CONCLUSIONS

An analytical/numerical method was demonstrated as a convenient way to determine fracture parameters at interfacial cracks in laminated composites. Results for the crack face contact region, stress intensity factors and energy release rates for a central delamination in $[\pm\Theta/90]_s$ laminates in three point bending were presented. Cracks with both small and large contact regions were considered. It was found that crack growth was unstable, except for small cracks and certain layup angles, Θ . In addition, the present results were compared with results in the literature obtained by the virtual crack closure integral technique for the special case of cross-ply laminates and close agreement was found. Overall, the method used

provides an effective way to analyze interfacial cracks and delaminations in composite plates subjected to transverse loads or low velocity impacts.

REFERENCES

1. Sun, C.T. and Manoharan, M.G. (1989). Growth of Delamination Cracks Due to Bending in a $[90_5/0_5/90_5]$ Laminate, *Composites Science and Technology*, 34: 365-377.
2. Rikards, R., Buchholz, F.G. and Wang, H. (1995). Finite Element Analysis of Delamination Cracks in Bending of Cross-Ply Laminates, *Mechanics of Composite Materials and Structures*, 2: 281-294.
3. Raju, I.S., Crews, J.H. and Aminpour, M.A. (1988). Convergence of Strain Energy Release Rate Components for Edge-Delaminated Composite Laminates, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, 30(3): 383-396.
4. Tong, P. and Pian, T.H.H. (1973). On the Convergence of the Finite Element Method for Problems with Singularity, *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, 9: 313-321.
5. Rybicki, E.F. and Kanninen, M.F. (1977). A Finite Element Calculation of Stress Intensity Factors by a Modified Crack Closure Integral, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, 9: 931-938.
6. Raju, I.S. (1987). Calculation of Strain-Energy Release Rates with Higher Order and Singular Finite Elements, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, 28(3): 251-274.
7. Sun, C.T. and Jih, C.J. (1987). On Strain Energy Release Rates for Interfacial Cracks in Bi-Material Media, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, 28(1): 13-20.
8. Penado, F.E. (2000). Determination of Stress Intensity Factors in Cracked Bonded Composite Joints, *Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials*, 13(3): 174-189.
9. Ting, T.C.T. and Chou, S.C. (1981). Edge Singularities in Anisotropic Composites, *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, 17: 1057-1068.
10. Comninou, M. (1977). Interface Crack with Friction in the Contact Zone, *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, 44: 780-781.
11. Muller, D.E. (1956). A Method for Solving Algebraic Equations Using an Automatic Computer, *Mathematical Tables and Computations*, 10: 208-215.
12. Press, W.H., Teukolsky, S.A., Vetterling, W.T. and Flannery, B.P. (1992). *Numerical Recipes in Fortran*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
13. Dongarra, J.J., Bunch, J.R., Moler, C.B. and Stewart, G.W. (1979). *LINPACK Users' Guide*, Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics, Philadelphia.
14. Penado, F.E. (2000). Analysis of Singular Regions in Bonded Joints, *International Journal of Fracture*, 105(1): 1-25.
15. Gross, B. and Mendelson, A. (1972). Plane Elastostatic Analysis of V-Notched Plates, *International Journal of Fracture Mechanics*, 8:267-276.
16. Carpenter, W.C. (1984). A collocation procedure for determining fracture mechanics parameters at a corner, *International Journal of Fracture*, 24:255-266.
17. COSMOS/M User Guide, Version 2.8. (2002). Structural Research and Analysis Corporation, Los Angeles, California.
18. Buchholz, F.G., Rikards, R. and Wang H. (1997). Computational Analysis of Interlaminar Fracture of Laminated Composites, *International Journal of Fracture*, 86: 37-57.
19. Penado, F.E. (2001). Out-of-Plane Coupling Effects on Stress Intensity Factors at Interface Cracks in Composite Lap Joints, *Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials*, 14(3): 178-200.
20. Comninou, M. (1977). The Interface Crack, *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, 44: 631-636.
21. Gautesen, A.K. and Dundurs, J. (1988). The Interface Crack under Combined Loading, *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, 55: 580-586.
22. Rice, J.R. (1968). A Path Independent Integral and the Approximate Analysis of Strain Concentrations by Notches and Cracks, *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, 35: 379-386.
23. Qu, J. and Bassani, J.L. (1993). Interfacial Fracture Mechanics for Anisotropic Bimaterials, *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, 60: 422-431.